

Synthesis of 3-aryl-2-tert.butylimino-6-*p*-tolylimino-4-(*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl)-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides and their antibacterial and antifungal studies

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Some 3-aryl-2-tert.butylimino-6-*p*-tolylimino-4-*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines (hydrochlorides) have been prepared by the interaction of 2-(*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl)-1-aryl-5-*p*-tolyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets and tert.butyl isocyanodichloride. These compounds show good to moderate antibacterial and antifungal activities. All products are optically active.

Most of the naturally occurring thioglucosides may be regarded as sulphur containing organic compounds in which the thiol hydrogen has been substituted by glucosyl radical and are associated with wide spectrum of biological activities¹. The study of alkyl/aryl isocyanodichlorides revealed that the reactions involved by nucleophilic displacement on both chlorides². In continuation of our earlier work³, several 3-aryl-2-tert.butylimino-6-*p*-tolylimino-4-(*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl)-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines hydrochlorides (3a-g) were prepared and screened for their antimicrobial activities. All compounds are optically active⁴.

Results and discussion

When the interaction of tert.butyl isocyanodichloride (1) has been carried out with 2-(*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl)-1-phenyl-5-*p*-tolyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (2) in refluxing benzene for 4 h evolution of hydrogen chloride was noticed. The viscous residue on trituration was converted in to pale yellow solid, m.p. 119°C. It was acidic to litmus and gave effervescences with aqueous sodium bicarbonate. It was found nondesulphurizable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. Its warm ethanolic solution when treated with ethanolic picric acid, afforded a picrate. The UV spectral data at 0.01% g concentration was obtained as 280, 310, 340, 370 and 400 nm. The IR spectrum revealed bands⁵ at 2968 (C-H of Ar-H), 1729 (C=O), 1598 (C=N), 1269 (C-N), 710 (C-S), 850 (*D*-glucopyranosyl ring deformation)⁶. Its ¹H NMR spectrum displayed signals⁵ at δ 8.06–6.26 (29H, m, Ar-H), 5.89–4.40 (7H, m, glucopyranosyl ring)⁷, 2.30 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 1.62–1.06 (9H, m, (CH₃)₃-C). Its mass spectrum showed peaks⁸ at *m/z* 996 (M⁺ 23), 579 (100), 475 (46), 391 (22), 353 (18), 307 (43), 231 (100), 154 (100), 136 (100), 106 (100). On the basis of

all above facts the compound was assigned the structure 3-phenyl-2-tert.butylimino-6-*p*-tolylimino-4-*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines (hydrochlorides) (3a).

When the interaction of tert.butyl isocyanodichloride was extended to other 2-(*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl)-1-aryl-5-*p*-tolyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (2) in dry benzene medium, the related 3-aryl-2-tert.butylimino-6-*p*-tolylimino-4-(*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl)-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides (3) were isolated (Table 1).

Probable mechanism of formation of 3 is depicted in Scheme 1.

TBG : Tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl

R : (a) phenyl, (b) *o*-tolyl, (c) *m*-tolyl, (d) *p*-tolyl, (e) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (f) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (g) *p*-Cl-phenyl

Scheme 1

Table 1. Data of compounds 3a-g^a

Compd.	Yield (%)	$[\alpha]_D^{25}$ CHCl ₃	Picrates M.p.(°C)
3a	76	+ 119.04 ^b (c 0.164)	115
b	83	-66.66 ^b (c 0.156)	184 (d)
c	71	+ 27.47 ^b (c 0.364)	167 (d)
d	87	-116.27 ^b (c 0.172)	148 (d)
e	77	-107.14 ^b (c 0.280)	154-155 (d)
f	73	-125.00 ^b (c 0.240)	163 (d)
g	79	-116.27 ^b (c 0.172)	151 (d)

^aSatisfactory C, H, N and S analysis obtained for all compounds as hydrochlorides.

The compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity against various pathogenic Gram +ve and Gram -ve bacteria such as *S. aureus* (zone of inhibition 9–18 mm), *P. vulgaris* (10–15 mm), *Pseudomonas* (10–17 mm), *Bacillus* (12–16 mm), *E. coli* (12–18 mm) and *Salmonella* (12–17 mm) by cup-plate method⁹ at a concentration of 100 µg/ml⁻¹ in DMF using standard co-trimazine (25 µg/ml⁻¹) for bacteria **3f** and **3g** showed much activity against *S. aureus* and *Pseudomonas*. **3e** was found most active against all bacteria under study. **3a**, **3c** and **3d** showed enhance activity against *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas* and *Salmonella* respectively.

Antifungal activity was tested by cup-plate method at a concentration of 100 µg/ml⁻¹ in DMF by using greseofulvin (10 µg/ml⁻¹) as a standard against *A. niger* (11–18 mm) and *Fusarium* (00–15 mm). All compounds showed poor activity against above fungi, where as **3d**, **c** and **d** were inactive.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The UV was recorded on Systronic UV spectrometer, 119 pc pascal, version 1.5. IR spectras were recorded on Shimadzu 8201 PC (KBr) spectrophotometer; ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on FAB mass spectrometer. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel-G plates.

Tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl bromide was prepared¹⁰ by the interaction of brominating reagent and glucopyranose pentabenzate. The *S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamide (**2**) were prepared¹⁰ by the interaction of tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl bromide and aryl thiocarbamides. The 2-(*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl)-1-aryl-5-*p*-tolyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**3**) were prepared¹¹ by the interaction of *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate and appropriate (*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl)-1-aryl isothiocarbamide. Tert.butyl isocyanodichloride was prepared by passing chlorine gas through the solution of tert.butyl isothiocyanate in chloroform.

3-Aryl-2-tert.butylimino-6-*p*-tolylimino-4-(*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl)-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochloride (**3a-g**): To a clear solution of 2-(*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl)-1-aryl-5-*p*-tolyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (0.005 *M*) the tert.butyl isocyanodichloride (0.005 *M*) was mixed and then it was refluxed on boiling water bath for 3 h.

The benzene was distilled off and the viscous mass on

trituration several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) afforded the pale yellow solid (75–87%) which was crystallised from aqueous ethanol.

(**3b**): λ_{max} 280, 310, 340, 370, 400 nm; IR (KBr) 2971 (Ar-C-H), 1729 (C=O), 1598 (C=N), 1269 (C-N), 850 (glucopyranosyl C-H deformation), 710 (C-S); ¹H NMR δ 8.18–6.23 (28H, m, Ar-H), 5.92–4.44 (7H, m, glucopyranosyl ring), 2.25 (6H, s, 2Ar-CH₃), 1.06–1.26 (9H, m, (CH₃)₃-C); *m/z* 639, 579 (100), 475, 353, 248, 231, 154, 136, 105.

(**3g**): λ_{max} 280, 310, 340, 370, 400 nm; IR (KBr) 3067 (Ar-C-H), 1729 (C=O), 1601 (C=N), 1268 (C-N), 850 (glucopyranosyl C-H deformation), 710 (C-S); ¹H NMR δ 8.06–6.26 (28H, m, Ar-H), 5.9–4.1 (7H, m, glucopyranosyl ring), 2.34 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 1.06–1.23 (9H, m, (CH₃)₃-C); *m/z* 639, 579 (100), 475, 353, 289, 231, 154, 136, 105.

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